

Crop management

Ecological conditions for axillary bud sprouting of ratooning rice

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We studied the relationship between ratoon tiller number and ecological conditions in southern Sichuan Province, 1987-88, using hybrid rice variety Shanyou 63.

Planting density for the first season was 28 hill/m². N was applied basally at 135 kg/ha (N:P:K = 1:0.5:0.5). Urea at 112.5 kg/ha was applied as topdressing 15 d after full heading to encourage axillary bud sprouting. The main crop was harvested at 33 cm

height. Ecological conditions during axillary bud sprouting of the ratooning stubble are shown in the table.

Optimum ecological conditions for ratoon tillering were 25-26.0 °C daily average temperature and 84-85% hu-

midity (type VI).

A key factor in obtaining higher yields in ratoon rice is to synchronize the sprouting stage of axillary bud with ecological conditions. □

Ratoon tiller of rice under different ecological conditions in the South of Sichuan, China.

Ecological conditions during axillary bud sprouting stage			Ecological condition type	Ratoon tillers/m ²	Productive panicles/m ²	Grain yield (t/ha)
Daily average temperature (°C)	Humidity (%)	Sunshine (h)				
22.8	92.2	1.1	I	218.4	179.1	0.5
23.1	90.6	1.4	II	257.6	214.6	0.7
23.8	87.8	2.1	III	257.6	242.2	1.3
24.9	86.9	3.2	IV	282.8	271.7	1.6
25.2	82.5	4.8	V	322.0	298.9	2.3
25.6	84.6	4.4	VI	428.4	399.9	3.4
26.2	84.6	5.0	VII	288.4	261.7	1.9
26.8	82.9	6.2	VIII	277.2	252.9	1.6

Plant populations for higher productivity in Basmati-type scented rice

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IET8579 (CRM8-5078-388-212), a 125-d mutant of Basmati 370, has the qualitative grain characters of Basmati 370, and a 46% higher yield potential. We worked out the population required to improve its productivity under transplanted conditions.

Five plant population levels achieved through different interrow and intrarow spacings were tested during 1988 wet season in a randomized block design with four replications.

Crop yield did not vary significantly among 20- × 10-cm and 15- × 15-cm spacing (see table). At closer spacings (10 × 10 cm and 15 × 10 cm), although number of panicles per unit area was higher, grain yield decreased because of fewer filled spikelets per panicle and

Effect of spacing on yield components and field of scented rice IET8579.

Spacing (cm)	Hills/m ²	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	Spikelets/panicle	Unfilled spikelets/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)
10 × 10	100	2.3	288	0.85	34.5	24.5	18.1
15 × 10	66	2.6	286	0.94	46.0	23.0	19.0
20 × 10	50	2.9	283	1.06	48.8	21.0	19.3
15 × 15	44	2.8	282	1.05	46.8	21.5	19.3
20 × 15	33	2.4	270	1.08	48.0	21.4	19.3
LSD (0.05)		0.2	ns	0.12	8.0	ns	ns

lower panicle weight. At wider spacing (20 × 15 cm), panicle production was

lower despite higher numbers of filled spikelets and higher panicle weight. □

Integrated pest management – diseases

Improved method for bioassay of pesticides

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The microbial assay of pesticides uses solid media to enable measurement of

average diametric growth. But this method only accounts for average diametric growth; it does not account for circular growth of the pathogen. Total radial growth is not measured.

We studied the growth of *Rhizoctonia solani* on standard potato dextrose agar medium mixed with 100 pp *Aegle marmelos* essential oil as an inhibitor. The experiment was re-

Comparison of average diametric growth and radial growth of *R. solani* in *A. marmelos* essential oil.

peated four times with three replications each time.

Treated petri plates were incubated at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The data were computed by the formula $3.14 \times r^2$ (area measurement technique). The average diametric growth was always less than total radial growth (see figure).

Differences of a given growth ranged between 0.99 and 25%. When inhibition was 50% with the diametric growth measurement method, the same growth was only 25% by the area measurement method.

The difference increased from 0 to 50%, then decreased from 51 to 100%—the difference at 51% corresponds to the difference at 49, etc. There is a consistent 0.02% decrease between two adjacent units calculated by the area measurement method.

The method holds good for both sporulating and nonsporulating fungi. When fungal growth was irregular, however, this method was not accurate either. □

Joint infection of rice by *Sclerotium oryzae* Catt., *Sclerotium rolfsii* Sacc., and *Monographella albescens*

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During disease surveys of several foothill and upland ricefields in four districts of Manipur 1985-86, we noticed cases of sheath rot (ShR) fungus *Monographella albescens* (Thumen) Parkinson, Sivanesan and Booth associated with stem or foot rot disease. We collected 100 ShR-

diseased rice plants randomly from Imphal, Thoubal, Bishnupur, and Senapati districts. Those that also showed symptoms of stem- and foot rot-disease were separated and the disease isolated on potato dextrose agar (PDA).

Potted rice plants were inoculated at the late boot stage with 5-d-old cultures of *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*; control plants were treated with PDA medium alone. When disease symptoms appeared, prepared mycelial fragments from a 6-d-old culture of ShR fungus were sprayed on both diseased and control plants. Inoculated plants were maintained at 90% relative humidity.

Only two sclerotium-producing fungi, *S. oryzae* and *S. rolfsii*, were consistently associated with ShR (Table 1). The association of *M. albescens* with *S. oryzae* was higher than with *S. rolfsii*.

Rice plants infected with either *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii* were significantly more susceptible to ShR fungus (Table 2). □

Table 1. Association of *M. albescens* with *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*. Manipur Agricultural College, Imphal, India, 1985-86.

District	Plants analyzed (no.)	<i>M. albescens</i> association (%) with	
		<i>S. oryzae</i>	<i>S. rolfsii</i>
Imphal	100	8	2
Thoubal	100	5	4
Bishnupur	100	10	3
Senapati	100	6	3

Table 2. Severity of *M. albescens* on rice plants infected with either *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*. Manipur Agricultural College, Imphal, India, 1985-86.

Source of infection	<i>M. albescens</i>		Disease incidence (%)
	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (no.)	
<i>S. oryzae</i>	20	19	95
<i>S. rolfsii</i>	20	17	85
Control	20	5	25
LSD (0.05)	-	3	-

Influence of carbendazim concentration on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *Rhizoctonia solani*

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We studied the effect of different concentrations of carbendazim on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *R. solani*.

The culture filtrates of *R. solani*